

INTERNET ODOB AXLOQI

Termiz davlat pedagogika instituti talabasi

XOLYOROVA DILNURA

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada internet tarmog'idan foydalanish qoidalari hamda global kompyuter tarmog'i haqida yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Kompyuter, internet, texnologiya, kibershoh.

Abstract: This article describes the rules of using the Internet and the global computer network.

Key words: Computer, internet, technology, cyber king.

Аннотация: В данной статье описаны правила пользования Интернетом и глобальной компьютерной сетью.

Ключевые слова: компьютер, интернет, технология, кибер-король.

Currently, there are forms of communication, forms and methods of communication, and most of them are related to modern technical capabilities, in particular, they are provided using the global computer network - the Internet (Internet). This is primarily due to the fact that humanity has made a giant leap in the development of science and technology, which has opened up new opportunities for human activity. The emergence and development of digital and computer technologies and the subsequent mass distribution of personal computers opened a new type of "computer-computer" interaction and the Internet network for "computer-computer" interaction. Added MAN-computer-Man" communication capability. It should be noted that the Internet is developing very quickly. Thus, today the Internet has about 15 million subscribers in more than 150 countries of the world, and the monthly network volume increases by 7-10%.

A number of specific features of communication using computer networks should be taken into account. These features lead to the development of new forms and styles of interaction and the emergence of a unique Internet etiquette.

1. Do not forget that through a dead network and computer electronics you communicate with a living person and often with many people. Remember the environment of anonymity and permission - that the other end of the wire is the same person as you. Writing an electronic message, imagine that everyone tells the truth to the face, and you are not ashamed of your words.

2. Follow the network in the same rules that you follow in real life. Violation of human relations, moral rules or normative laws of public life Networks are relatively punishable for you, but will your conscience be cleared?

3. Don't forget that you are in cyber king! Its boundaries are much wider than those of ordinary humanity, and different parts may have their own laws. Therefore, focus on a new type of communication on the network, learn its laws and accept their priority. For example, news, a forum or even a channel has relevant, local rules, local rules - read them before sending your first message! And most importantly, remember the unwritten rules.

4. Check out other people's time and thoughts! Only if necessary - and in this case you can always help and support your colleagues. However, do not drag other users into trivial areas - otherwise you will eventually stop communicating with you. Remember that network time is not only limited, but also very expensive! And in addition to your problems, your interlocutors can also be on their own.

5. Try to look decent in the eyes of your interlocutors! Save your time on the "conventions" of good tone rules or, say, grammar and spelling rules. Even sincere compliments lose weight and believability with grammatical and spelling errors and incorrect form.

6. Do not ignore the advice of experts and share your knowledge with others! Answer your questions to those who have invested your time. But do not rush to trash the question of another user, no matter how funny and simple it seems to you, do not send a message.

7. Pay attention to frustrations. No etiquette is forbidden to enter the discussions, but do not go to Brahi and curses - even if your Vezavari consciously annoys you.

8. Respect not only your own privacy, but the privacy of others! If for some reason you want to remain anonymous online, acknowledge these rights and your interviewer. In addition, even if you are "with an open king", you have the right to anonymity and privacy. The pastures of this rule: do not publish information from your personal letters without the consent of their senders, do not dig in other mail computers, other foreign computers!

9. Do not abuse your authority and influence the network! Trust is easy to gain and lose!

10. Be tolerant of the shortcomings of people around you! Don't look at it, don't watch your parameter or be, save them yourself! At the end of the day, it is very polite to familiarize yourself with these rules.

Summary

In conclusion, we can say that the Internet is an almost universal means of intercultural communication, which contributes to the rapprochement of peoples and national and international self-awareness. Currently, there are many ways to communicate on the

Internet, such as e-mail, forums, various conferences, chat rooms, network games, and many others. But communication using computer networks has a number of specific features. First, it reflects the ability to convey many people in different parts of the world at the same time and therefore the ability to live in different cultures; secondly, the impossibility of using most communication and self-restraint; thirdly, a decrease in the emotional component of communication; and fourth, Anonymity and reduction of psychological risk in the communication process. These features lead to the development of a unique Internet etiquette with rules of illegal communication in which you can enjoy and benefit from virtual communication.

References:

1. Belinskaya E., Zhichkina A. Modern research Virtual communication: problems, hypotheses, results. - M.: Uniti-Dana, 2004. - 165 p.
2. Gorvsky Yu. Back to the Future // World of the Internet. No. 10. - M., 2001.- 35 p.
3. Chichkina A. Social-psychological aspects of communication on the Internet. - m .: Dashkov and CO., 2004. - 117 p.

